

Automatic Breaking NEWS Application

Puneeth B. R.^{1,2} & Nethravathi P. S.³

¹ Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, India

² Assistant Professor, Department of M.C.A, NMAMIT, Nitte, Karkala, India

OrcidID: 0000-0003-1985-0411; E-mail: puneethbr9@gmail.com

³ Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, India

OrcidID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; E-mail: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Current generation completely relays upon the electronic Media. The main objective of this news application is to provide the updated and breaking news to the users of the system. A JWT token is used for user authentication process. The user can read the article of his interest by selecting the category. The application will simplify the job of the admin by automating some of the process using cron jobs. This news application is built to meet the requirements of current generation people and to update them about the daily news, breaking news and latest headlines in different fields around the world

Keywords- News Application, Json Web Token, Cron, android, digital

1.INTRODUCTION:

There used to be a time when people went to shops to buy the newspapers or waited for the newspapers delivery person to get updated on the day-to-day news. With the widespread use of smartphones, in today's generation, a news application has almost replaced the newspapers, for several advantages that it offers. A news application provides flexibility, thereby providing a seamless reader experience. This digital solution of creating a news application has not only contributed to the ecosystem by saving papers, but also has made people's life much easier. The news applications that are currently prevailing today has the feature of category-based filtering to match the interest of each user. There are several categories like "Entertainment", "Sports", "Politics", "Technology" etc., based on which the reader can selectively choose the category of his/her interest. The User Interface in the present news applications has made these apps user-friendly. Every news article is pictorially represented with images, having a brief summary of the event. It has also hyperlinked to the videos/complete articles if any. This drastically saves reader's time in getting a glance of every article. Some of these applications have a section dedicated to readers' comments. This lets the readers share their point of view and keeps other readers more engaged into the events. The news apps also take surveys/ polls in the intermediate sections, which helps to know the readers' perspectives to the real-world problems. The news application also provides real-time updates as and when the events occur, through the notifications. The reader is notified in the notifications section, so that he/she is updated with the news without even opening the news app. The application also has a section for advertisements, which displays only relevant ads based on the reader profile. The present applications also have a feature of sharing any specific news article with others on various applications like WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter etc., letting the reader to broadcast the article in a larger scale. In an attempt to provide a quality experience to the readers, the news application has not only replaced the newspapers, but also have shown tremendous

development to keep the readers engaged. There are continuous efforts in making the application better by adding new features through application updates. Making this application freely available has made these present in every smartphone today

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Rasool Bux Palh et al design and Develop CMS for Sindhi e-newspaper by using the searching techniques. Methods/analysis Existing e-newspapers are not implementing any CMS with searching techniques [1]. Aakash Rastogi et al mentioned in this paper like a news and content aggregator site scrapes or collect useful information from all over the web and then the whole collection is sorted or categorized accordingly and posted or published at a single website for the convenience of the visitor. RepNews is an online platform that fulfill the service-oriented needs of the users across the globe [2]. Manoj Kumar Srivastav et al the present a paper it is tried to study how a mathematical function can works in the three stages of web CMS. A CMS is a web application that run on web server to help facilitate creating a website. Also, it is tried to study mathematically regarding working of database in web CMS [3]. Marios Constantinides et al report a series of three studies addressing key issues in the development of adaptive news app interfaces. First surveyed user's news reading preferences and behaviours then implemented and deployed an Android news app that logs users interactions with the app [4]. Garg et al expressed like news is increasingly accessed on smartphones and tablets, the need for personalising news app interactions is apparent. Report a series of three studies addressing key issues in the development of adaptive news app interfaces. first surveyed user's news reading preferences and behaviours; analysis revealed three primary types of reader, then implemented an Android news application that users can be interacted with the app. Final evaluation was adaptive user interfaces for each reader type [5]. Marios Constantinides investigates novel "smart personalization" methods for news apps. It's looking into how people read news on their smartphones. It's working on a prototype news app that can recognise different types of news reading behaviour and adapt its display and interaction methods accordingly, in other words, an app that forms "habits." The deployed app is currently being evaluated over time [6].

3.EXISTING SYSTEM:

In the existing system there was a separate Content Management System for the mobile application and for the website. The admin had to enter the data for both of this. As there were multiple servers being run in order to maintain the mobile applications and the website, the cost incurred was higher. Since there were multiple servers in the existing system, the maintenance was a tedious and time-consuming process. The existing system required a lot of manual intervention by the admin in order to maintain smooth operation of data. The existing system had fixed templates, which restricted the admin's ability to create dynamic and rich content.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

This system's aim is to increase automation thereby allowing the client to focus on more relevant tasks such as content creation and curation. In this system we are maintaining one content management system for both mobile application and the website which saves the time. The proposed system runs on a single server thereby reducing the maintenance load drastically. The proposed system includes automation methods such as cron to help reduce the admins workload. The proposed system uses a combination of HTML and native data to provide the admin and the end users with a cleaner and refined interaction with the application/website.

5.MODULE DESCRIPTION:

Users of the system:

Admin: Admin can login by using the username and the password. He can add the news, photos, videos, polls, advertisements, categories, results, regions. He can approve or report the comments.

User: User can read the news, view photos, videos and then by login using the username and the password and can add comments user can filter the news by selecting category and can view news articles.

Modules of the Admin

Login: Admin can log in using his/her email and password, and system will check whether the entered username and password is valid or not, if it is valid then system takes admin to content management system.

Category: Admin can create different categories. He can edit created category by changing category name, visibility, display order, etc. Here he can create subcategory for a particular category by assigning the value for the field parent. He can delete created category.

District: Admin can create different districts. He can edit the districts by changing its name, order or visibility. He can delete the district.

Story: Admin can add the news by entering the news details and he can assign a news to a particular category or to a particular district. He can add photos and videos for the news and also, he can embed Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube content. He can edit the news by changing the title, highlights, body, visibility, photos, videos or other information. He can delete the news.

Photo album: Admin can create photo album and add photos to it. He can edit the photo album by changing the title, caption of the photos, adding photos or deleting photos. He can delete the photo album.

Video: Admin can add videos by providing the video URL. By using the URL, video thumbnail, duration, number of likes, comments and shares are retrieved and stored. He can edit the video title, visibility or description. He can delete the videos

Polls: It is used to find out the opinion of the user's about a event Admin can add questions and options with image and admin can set the lifespan for the visibility of a particular poll. He can edit the polls by changing the questions, options, lifespan and visibility.

Advertisement: Admin can add advertisements for the different products. He can edit the advertisement by adding or removing images, by changing the refresh time, title, category or district.

Live stream: Admin can add the links of live events. He can enable or disable by using is visible field link make be channel live, youtube live etc.

Push notifications: Admin can send notifications to the users about the news, videos photos, live streams and updated categories to the user's push notification is sent using crone job it is a job scheduling command in that will can set time when the notification should be sent.

Comments: It is module where all user's comments can be viewed by admin. He can approve or report the comments unwanted comments.

Results: This module is used during the election of different zones like country, state, constituencies and can add party details. Admin as a right to enable or disable the module.

Modules of User:

Login Registered user can log in using the email and password and system will check whether the entered username and password is valid or not, if it is valid then the user can add comment to articles.

Registration: New user can register by entering his or her details. The registered user details is stored in the system.

Profile: It stores the profile details of the user. User can view and edit the name, gender, profile photo and other information.

Polls: It is used to find out the opinion of the user's about a event. User can select and save his option for the poll. User can view the past polls and answered polls with answer.

District: User can select the district so that he can read the news about that particular district. Its is a filter which is used to categorize the news articles.

Category: User can select the category so that he can read the news related to that category. Its is mainly made engage by category of viewers.

Live stream: User watch live events on their smartphone/computer using live stream it is helpful while traveling or outside.

Push notification: User will get the notifications about the news, videos, photos, live stream and categories. It will help the user to get information without opening the application.

Comments: User can read the comments of other users. He/she can also add comments for any article by logging into the application.

Search: User can search for any particular article based on the title of the article.

6. SYSTEM DESIGN:

Use case diagram: Use Case Diagrams, also known as behaviour diagrams, depict the relationship between actors or participants and a set of actions. The system boundary will enclose this set of actions or use cases, which may or may not be related to one another. The information gain computed for each attribute will be used to divide tupelos.

Use case diagram for Admin: The Use case of the admin is displayed where the admin has a full access on system where he can add, edit, delete, and display category, district, story, news articles, photo album, videos, polls, review, comments.

Fig 1: Use case diagram for admin.

Use case diagram for User: The Use case of the user is displayed where the user's has a limited access on system where he can select the category, view news details, view the displayed comment and he can login and add comments and answer the polls.

Fig 2: Use case diagram for User

Activity diagram for admin: The Activity diagram of admin is displayed, It state's the activity's done by the admin they are login to the system by using username and password and adding, viewing, editing story(news), category, district, photo album, video, mobile ads, web ads, result and viewing and approval of the comment.

Fig3: Activity diagram for admin

7. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND RESULT:

User was allowed to use this application in his Desktop or smartphone, screenshots were taken as a result for this study. The first user must sign up in order to access the application, which ensures its security. Before this experiment, predicted user error handling with pop-up messaging was done, such as entering invalid data in fields, not selecting a field before clicking on an action button, and so on. The outcome will be displayed in the form of screen shots below.

Fig 4: Dashboard

Fig 5: News Articles Based on Category

8. SCOPE FOR FUTURE PROSPECTS:

- In coming days, it can be made possible for the users to choose the language of their interest.
- Makes the server able to handle more users. It leads to application will fast and more relevant.
- Makes use of better cache mechanism in order to provide quicker response.
- It is possible to implement a location feature with automation, which means that as the user moves from one city to another, the local news will change accordingly.

9. CONCLUSION:

This news application is a news portal developed using python, django rest framework. In this application user need not to sign in to read the news articles. Only the polls and comment section require user login. The user is authenticated using the json web tokens (JWT). This system has only one admin account. Creation of admin in the client end is restricted to avoid the misuse. This application is user friendly there is no special knowledge required to use the applications. This application will ensure that the information/news provided are accurate and which brings harmony in society.

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